
OPPORTUNITIES OF USING INNOVATIVE APPROACHES AND METHODS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays the usage of innovative technologies in the methodology of teaching foreign language has become increasingly important. This article provides changes in methods of teaching and the latest innovative technologies in the process of learning foreign languages on the part of the teacher, also it describes Finland's education system and techniques that reached at peak in today's world. Innovative educational technologies are, first of all, information and communications technologies, closely connected with computerized education application. The main issues in innovative technologies use are the structure of computer training programs, their content and optimal arranging of Web-environment.

Keywords: *Foreign languages, Innovative technologies, Methods, Creativity, Finland's education system.*

Modern conditions require not only the use of new technologies in teaching foreign languages, but also changes in methods of teaching and the ability to introduce the latest innovative technologies in the process of learning foreign languages. Universities of higher education tend to active methods of teaching, that are directed at forming students' independence, flexibility, critical thinking. In fact, one of the most powerful source of the students' cognitive activity, developing their creativity, interests, skills and other mental characteristics is innovative technologies. The global web provides a unique opportunity for students to use authentic texts, communicate with native-speakers, creating natural language environment and forming the abilities of intercultural cooperation. Access to the Internet creates incentives to know a foreign language fluently. Internet as a means of transferring information is especially urgent for students' independent work after classes. The most important goal, according to scientists is the formation of a secondary language personality. Students must take a new language to a fundamentally new level. To do

this, it is important to separate it from the mother tongue, in order to avoid errors in perception [1].

Methods and Approaches of Foreign Languages Teaching

As technology developing by opening opportunities for a lot of fields that makes them to change their methods ,techniques, attitudes and approaches as well.

Innovative methods effected to the process of learning and teaching foreing languages. Modern stage is characterized by careful selection of methods of foreign languages teaching.Particular emphasis today is made on modern information technology and actual trends.Use of modern technologies, such as computers, Internet-resources, special educational multimedia programs, as well as modern technical equipment allows to optimize the teaching process. The advantages of using innovative technologies are following:

- increase of motivation and enthusiasm of students and teachers through active involvement in the process of live communication, possibilities of language acquisition are increasing thanks to the cooperation, interaction and communication in learning language;

- great potential for a variety of teaching methods and teaching to the needs of each student;

- job satisfaction, where the result is visible after each section;

- self-education of student’s personality through the skills to locate, retrieve, evaluate and analyze relevant information;

- intensification of the educational process that allows to rationally organize the educational process, both in the classroom and in the condition of independent work of students.

- professional development – communication skills of students and teachers.[2]

Therefore, innovative technology essentially enhance and differentiate the method of teaching. Intellectual, creative search comes up to take the place of monotonous work. It helps to create a personality of a new type, active, purposeful, directed on constant self-education and development. Computers application encourages the optimization of teaching management, efficiency increase of study process, saves teachers’ time for the work with teaching material, simplifying its search, analysis, selection and gives an opportunity of application of new organizational forms of teaching.

According to scientific calculations of national and foreign scientists, the term “method” has two basic meanings:

- A certain path to the goal, means to achieve the result.
- Complete methodological system and the fundamental direction of the learning process, which prevail in the various periods of the science development.

Modern stage is characterized by careful selection of methods of foreign languages teaching. Particular emphasis today is made on modern information technology and actual trends. There is a sort of selection of the Innovative Methods of Foreign Languages most effective methods, techniques and tools during the preparation of specialists in various fields.

During selection of innovative methods following criteria taken into account:

- Creating a comfortable and supportive atmosphere for student, promotion of natural interest and desire to learn a new foreign language.
- Involvement of emotions, feelings, experiences in the educational process to stimulate verbal, written and creative abilities.
- Use of the cognitive approach in the educational process
- Call to work with the language on their own at the level of emotional and physical capabilities [3].

Various forms of work will help to achieve these goals. Practical experience allows concluding that the personality and interests of the student directly affects the quality of foreign language understanding. To do this, it is important to use a variety of techniques and learning tools. By the end of the 20th century in pedagogy has accumulated a lot of interesting and effective methods and approaches. Scientists have enriched the methodology of foreign languages teaching, so it has become complex and multifaceted science.

The Modernization of the Process of Foreign Language.

Learning Mobile and qualified people are needed to the social, economic and spiritual development of the government. To solve the problem modernization of the learning process is made in accordance with the relevant requirements. In particular it relates to foreign languages teaching. Modernization involves changing of goals, the volume of mandatory content, as well as methods and tools for the development of new knowledge. Today there is a tendency to individualize the learning process and the use of new information technologies in the education system. Modern processes are focused on the saving of fundamental education. At present, there is no any country that can able to beat Finland's education system in the world. Finland was recently named the Happiest Country in the world by the United Nations World Happiness Report, for the fourth time in a row. One of Finland's attractions is their

education system. Its unorthodox education system is deemed to be one of the best in the world simply by going against the evaluation-driven, centralised model that many countries use.

- Why Finland has the best education system?
- How does Finland’s education system work?

They have longer class periods and much longer breaks in between. The overall system is not there to ram and cram the information to their students, but to create an environment of holistic learning.

- The education system in Finland consist of daycare programmes (for babies and toddlers);
 - A one year “pre-school”(age six);
 - The minimum age of starting elementary education in Finland is 7 years thus Finnish kids get to enjoy their childhood and kickstart their learning with their families rather than spending excessive time in schools.
 - The only mandatory test that Finnish students give is at the age of 16.
 - Finnish teachers only spend around 4 hours every day teaching in the classroom while they devote 2 hours every week for professional development.
 - The school system in Finland is wholly 100% state-funded.
 - The graduates from the top 10 percentile can only apply to become a Teacher in Finland.
 - Every teacher in Finland is a master’s degree holder which is completely subsidized by the country’s government.
 - On average, the starting salary of a teacher in Finland is somewhere around \$29,000.
 - Teachers are considered equivalent in status to doctors and lawyers in Finland.
 - In 2018, the literacy rate in Finland was 99.0%.
 - Finnish students spend only 20 hours a week at school.
 - Every student in Finland can speak 2-3 languages.
 - No competitions between Finnish schools since every academic institution has the same facilities as any other.
 - Students get to learn new things in schools from baking and industrial works to music and poetry.

- For every 45 minutes of learning in schools, Finnish students get to spend every 15 minutes for playing or leisure activities.
- Finnish students receive free healthy meals from their schools.
- Every Finnish student is provided special services that fit their special needs and requirements.
- The Finland education system also fosters the teacher-student relationship as every student gets the same teacher for up to 6 years in their school.
- The students get very less homework and almost finish up everything they get during the school hours only.
- The Finnish schools have mixed ability classes to nurture diverse interests and hobbies.

In Finland, a career as a teacher is highly sought after, to enter the studies in University really hard as only 10 per cent are taken to study teaching that makes its education system effective and productive at the same time.

It has been proven that traditional studies directed only to the transfer and maintenance of knowledge, skills and abilities, and do not demonstrate adequate performance. Modern language education system aimed at the formation of a multicultural identity, with the skills of self-analysis and systematization of new knowledge. For this purpose, used competence and culturological approaches. Information and computer technology can improve efficiency and create the conditions for self-study. Innovative methods is an integral part of the modernization of the whole system. Teachers should familiarize themselves with the most progressive approaches and later combine them and use in work.

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